

COORDINATION OF TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES OF GRINDING OF FRUIT PRODUCTS

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ANNOTATION

In the article, simirinko apples were taken as an experiment, where the analyzes and experimental works of the fruit production enterprise "Darmon Farm" in Yakkabog District, Kashkadarya Region were shown. One of the broadest problems of today is meeting people's needs with natural products and increasing their species.

Keywords. The number of rotations of the wheel disc, elementary knife cutting speed of raw fruit, the depth of immersion of the elementary knife into the raw fruit being cut, Simirenko is defined by the specific driving force of apple cutting, the Bucher HP5000 screw press.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье в качестве опыта были взяты яблоки симиринко, где показаны анализы и опытные работы плодородческого предприятия «Дармон Фарм» Яккабогского района Кашкадарьинской области. Одной из широчайших проблем современности является удовлетворение потребностей людей натуральными продуктами и увеличение их численности.

Ключевые слова. Число оборотов диска колеса, скорость нарезки элементарного ножа сырых плодов, глубина погружения элементарного ножа в нарезаемый плод Симиренко определяется удельной движущей силой резания яблок винтовым прессом Bucher HP5000.

Introduction. Simirenko apple is considered one of the most widespread double fruit plants of Kashkadarya region, this late-ripening plant differs from other types of apples by its surface roughness, in the technological process, cutting it with a machine knife is considered one of the main methods of creating a mathematical model[1].

Figure 1. Scheme of cutting simirenko apples with an elementary knife (charkhi).

Research method.. The density of the raw fruit being cut ρ , the specific cutting force of the fruit raw material σ ; the diameter of the circular blade is $2r$; blade thickness 2δ ; wheel angle 2α ; The thickness of cut fruit raw material is H ; the length of cut fruit raw material is $2l$; delivery speed of fruit raw materials ϑ_n ; the rotation speed of the apple is ϑ_0 ; the ratio of the rotation speed of the point on the blade edge g ; incoming speed of fruit raw material ϑ_n (angle of deviation λ) instantaneous height Δh , possibility of cutting fruit raw material, coefficient of friction of fruit raw material on blade (wheel) μ ; modulus of elasticity of fruit raw materials E . Results obtained during the cutting of Simirenko apples with a circular knife[2].

expressions:

The number of rotations of the wheel disc:

$$n = 30\lambda(v_n + v_a)/\pi r \quad (1)$$

elementary knife cutting speed of raw fruit:

$$\vec{v} = \vec{v}_a + \vec{v}_n + \vec{v}_a \quad (2)$$

the depth of immersion of the elementary knife into the raw fruit being cut:

$$h_i = \sum i, \quad (3)$$

where i - is the number of the elementary blade.

The entire calculation process is performed for every j -th elementary blade,

Number of views (point system) , dependence of the blade friction force on the line of force

fulfillment of the condition.

$$R_j = \frac{r-H-\Delta h}{\cos\varphi_j} < r. \quad (4)$$

As an initial value, the R_j value is taken for each i -elementary blade (wheel).

If the condition (4) is not fulfilled, the more the deviation step increases, the value of j will also increase.

Simirenko is defined by the specific driving force of apple cutting.

$$R_{yD_j} = \sigma + l_{H.P.K} \cdot \left(\frac{E\delta}{l}\right) \cdot (\sin\alpha + \mu\cos\alpha_{\varphi_i}) + 2\mu\left(h_i - \left(\frac{b_{Hi}}{2}\right) \cdot \operatorname{tg}\gamma - \delta \cdot \operatorname{ctg}\alpha_{\varphi_i} \cdot \left(\frac{E\delta}{l}\right) + \left(\frac{pl}{3}\right)\right) \cdot v_1^2 \cdot \operatorname{tg}^2\alpha_{\varphi_i} \quad (5)$$

Here is v_i - how to find the elementary blade speed vector value.

$$v_i = \sqrt{v_{0i}^2 + v_{\pi}^2 + v_a^2 + v_{0i} \cdot v_{\pi} \cdot v_a^2 \cdot \cos\gamma_i} \quad (6)$$

The total components of the cutting force of the Simirenko apple are determined by integrals, $i \rightarrow \infty$, $a \rightarrow \varphi_i$ the number of unprofitability of elementary blades is the ratio of the forces in the vertical and horizontal parts of the blade.

$$R_B = r \int_{\varphi_p}^{\varphi_y} R_{yD} [(\lambda \sin^2 \cdot \varphi) / (1 + \lambda^2 - 2\lambda \cos\varphi)] d\varphi \quad (7)$$

$$R_r = r \int_{\varphi_p}^{\varphi_y} R_{yD} [(\sin\varphi(\lambda\cos\varphi - 1)/(1 - \lambda^2 - 2\lambda\cos\varphi))] d\varphi$$

(8)

Moment on the shaft of a circular blade with forces applied to the edge:

$$M_{CHQ} = r^2 \int_{\varphi_p}^{\varphi_y} R_{yD} [(\sin\varphi(\lambda\cos\varphi - 1)/(1 + \lambda^2 - 2\lambda\cos\varphi))] d\varphi$$

(9)

(7) - (9) integration by numerical methods in the calculation of expressions it is not difficult to do on a computer.

Friction moment of Simirenko apple cut on side surfaces disk blade is equal to:

$$M_{YK} = 2\mu E(\delta/l) \cdot \Delta r \sum^{r_{\max}} 2\varphi_1 r_1. \quad (10)$$

Conclusion. Creating a mathematical model of the process of peeling Simirenko apples, how it differs from the processes of cutting other food products, semi-finished meat products, cheese, vegetables and others. This kind of mathematical model has a well-defined theoretical direction and it is possible to create it. After the process of cutting the fruits of Simirenko apples, the next step is the production process of fruit juice, the process of screw pressing is used to obtain apple juice. Between the shaft and the drum of the speed of the fruit at the time of fruit arrival (2 - 3 mm). In this regard, part of the fruit product passes through and is returned back under the influence of feedback. To calculate this process, it is necessary to find the value of the coefficient of return. This coefficient shows what part of the fruit's consumption is relative to the total flow in the state. the shaft is in constant motion. Theoretically, it cannot be calculated, it is determined experimentally by calculation. For this purpose, in the article, an experiment was conducted in the fruit production enterprise "Darmon farm" in the Yakkabog district of the Kashkadarya region.

Due to the value of the coefficient of return, the size of the cavity and therefore the type of the screw are only valid experimental data. for screw press

type Bucher HP5000. Experiments have shown that the level of return value varies slightly from batch to batch and depends on the characteristics of the instrumental non-dominant Simirenko apple, the average value of the return coefficient obtained from 30 experimental results is 0.078[3]

As a result of mathematical modeling, we obtained the expression for the dynamic state of the Bucher HP5000 screw press:

$$\left[\frac{V}{D_1 + D_2} \right] \left(\frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial p} \right) \left(\frac{d\Delta p}{dt} \right) = b_1 \Delta n_1 - a_1 \Delta n - a_2 \Delta p \quad (11)$$

Given:

$$a_1 = 1.844V_p,$$

$$a_2 = 1.844V_n p_1 \varepsilon^{-2} \left(\frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial p} \right),$$

(12)

V - free volume of location camera; D - a comprehensive compression module of fruit raw materials; $-D_2$ equivalent volume expansion coefficient; e - compression of fruit pulp in a level drum; P - pressure in the device; p_1, p - fruit raw materials and additional raw materials, n_1 - rotation frequency of the screw[4];

(11) - let's express the expression in the dimensionless state

$$T \dot{\phi} + \phi = k_1 \mu_1 - k_2 \mu_2 \quad (13)$$

Given:

$$\phi = \frac{\Delta p}{p_0}; \quad \mu_1 = \frac{\Delta b}{b_0}; \quad \mu_2 = \frac{\Delta n}{n_{\max}};$$

$$T = \frac{V_2}{D \left(\frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial p} \right)} a_2; \quad k_1 = \frac{a_3 b_0}{a_2 p_0}; \quad k_2 = \frac{a_1 n_{\max}}{a_2 p_0}; \quad (14)$$

As an object of automation in the production of fruit juice, through the regulatory influence channels of the screw press, Simirenko juice has (μ_1, μ_2 the

same time constant, but the difference in productivity depending on the type of fruits of different sizes has been noticed.

References

1. Ekpenyong E. E., Piotrovsky D. L. Research and selection of technical properties of automation of the pineapple juice production process [Text]
2. E. E. Ekpenyong, D. L. Piotrovsky // Scientific journal of KubSAU [Electronic resource].-Krasnodar: KubGAU,
3. Ekpenyong E. E., Piotrovsky D. L. Mathematical model of the cutting process pineapples with an elementary knife [Text] / E.E. Ekpenyong, D.L. Piotrovsky News of higher educational institutions. Food Technology
4. Gafurov Yu., Yakubov M.S. Avtomatizatsiya prosessov proizvodstva stekol'noy promishlennosti i umen'shenie finansovix poter'. Modernizatsiya sistemi mestnogo upravleniya: zarubejniy opit i reformi v Uzbekistane. Sbornik materialov mejdunarodnoy nauchno-prakticheskoy konferensii. G.Tashkent 2017 god 14 yyunya. 301-305 str.